

Gender construction in modern drama: A stylistic analysis of A Doll's House by Henry Ibsen

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Abstract

The study aims to explore the gender roles which are constructed in the first revolutionary modern drama. Ibsen has beautifully explored the condition of marginalized women of that time. When the drama was written the existing society had no concept of feminism. The study is qualitative under the descriptive paradigm. The researcher has collected the data from the play *A Doll's House* and analyzed it stylistically especially exploring implicit meanings (regarding gender roles) lying in rhetorical or figurative language used by Ibsen in *A Doll's House*. Women were restricted to the household as they were expected inferior creature but man were supposed to be the symbol of world power, symbol of authority, symbol of reputation and symbol of superiority. He was the head regarded as the decision maker. By going through the drama we analyze that this position of man at that time is clearly elaborated by Ibsen. When Nora says, I simply transferred from my father's hand to my husband's hand, her words show the decision power of man. Throughout the drama, Nora made many sacrifices and had faced many challenges by remaining consistent. The work of Ibsen is a best example for the foundation of feminism. The work of Shakespeare in Hamlet and Oscar Wild's work I the picture of dorian gray shows male dominance. But in their work, we find not so many supports for women. As in the work of Ibsen we can see had changed the thinking of women of that time.

Keywords: Gender roles, Figurative language, Stylistics, Symbol of authority, Symbol of reputation

1. Introduction

This literature of specific era is closely connected with its social, political, historical background. The writers of this era try to show deep awareness of their present environment in their creative work. Many writers can come forward to pretend themselves as social critics Victorian age was started in 1830. It was the era of Queen Victoria. The political condition of this era was divided between two parties' highs and Tories (Rooney, 2021). This era was full of contradictions, scientific discoveries, poverty, and religious unrest. It was a time of confident progress. Development of industries created many wealth benefits. The popular conviction of this era was work is a duty which is necessary for the pleasure of soul. But all these changes were not positive every time the basic needs and rights of ordinary people were also influenced the rapid change of urbanization and industrialization created contradictions between employers and workers. For the improvement of society very strong moral social and religious causes were put forward (Savant, 2021).

Correctness of laws should be examined up to that extent to which they promote most possible happiness of most-greatest number. Happiness is difficult to define because it does not mean to be timely emotions of a person but well-being advantages for a person obeying laws will bring happiness for people. One of the most important scenarios of Victorian era was liberalism. Liberalism was a political movement of this age that refers to defend the freedom for individuals (Sera-Shriar, 2021). The most important aspect of liberalism was economic theory of free trade. Liberalism was popular between both of the Whigs and Tories. It promotes an un-ended competition and challenged competition and challenged interference of government for industry and commerce.

1.1. Objective of the Study

The study aims to

- ❖ Understand how gender roles are constructed in modern drama "A Doll's House"
- ❖ To examine how gender roles are designated through the use of literature.

2. Literature Review

This chapter refers to the previous researches on gender and development to highlight the procedure of development, main approaches towards gender and development (John, 2021). It also analyze the sociology of gender in the light of theoretical perspectives and feminist frameworks. Moreover, this section includes fundamental questions and the concept of variation and universality for the work of Ibsen. It also explains the notion of feminism (Ayoub et al., 2021; Kriner & Lewis, 2021; Bechert, 2021) and of patriarchal society in the work of Ibsen. Doll's House represents woman's identity which can be used to give a change in gender identity under the influence of waves of feminism.

2.1. Theories of Gender Development

In relation to the development of the gender, most of the part is developed during childhood. In this regard, lets try to analyze the development of gender in the light of following theories.

- i. Cognitive Development Theory-Kohlberg (1966)
- ii. Gender Schema Theory-Bem (1981)
- iii. Social Learning Theory- Bandura & Walters (1977)

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According to cognitive development theory at every stage of learning the child thinks about gender in a characteristic way. Kohlberg explained that the gender learning process consist of following stages.

3. Research Methodology

Qualitative research is the gathering, examination and translation of extensive account and visual (i.e., non numerical) information to pick up bits of knowledge into a specific marvel of intrigue. Qualitative research strategies depend on various convictions and intended for various reason more than quantitative research techniques. For instance, subjective analysts don't really acknowledge the perspective of a steady, lucid, uniform world. They contend that all significance is arranged in a specific point of view or setting, and in light of the fact that alternate points of view and setting, the world has various implications, none of which is fundamentally more legitimate and more valid than other.

Account investigation of Narrative research is the investigation of how diverse people encounter their general surroundings; it includes a technique that enables individuals to recount the stories of their "storied lives". The specialist commonly concentrates on a solitary individual and accumulated information by gathering occasions about the individual's life. The scientist and members at that point build a composed record, known as a story, about the person's encounters and the implications the individual ascribe to the encounters. On account of the community idea of story deferential relationship another approach to consider account look into is that the tale of the marvel being explored and story is additionally the strategy for request being utilized by the scientist.

4. Data Analysis

4.1. Characterization

Characterization is a literary device which is used very appropriately by Ibsen in this play. The character of Nora in this play is of vital importance. We can see a very remarkable change in her character at the beginning of the play. Nora seems very happy. She was in a carefree mood. She had a very glowing personality she did shopping and answered Tol Torvald that they can be little extravagant because he has become a manager and will earn a fat salary. When Torvald teats Nora as "my little skylark" she never mind of his words. But at the end of the play we see Nora has changed. The loving and carefree woman has changed into a serious woman. She starts thinking about herself. Ton her it was more sacred to think about herself instead of thinking about her children and her husband. Her thinking about the outlook of life has changed. At the beginning, Nora was a devoted and self-sacrificing wife who take loan for the treatment of her husband. For taking loan it was necessary to have signature of her father on a band for surety. She forged the signature of have money from Karlstad she was very happy because of setting loan at that time she was unaware of that what she is doing after some time her act become a serious threat for her she has constantly been repaying the loan with interest in in instalments. She spend less to herself and did some copying work to return the money. She found pleasure that she had a saved her husband's life. She knew that if her husband set aware that she has saved his life his pride would be hurt. She therefore do many efforts of ride this secret.

Nora was very kind helpful to her friend. Mrs. Linde. He friend was now a widow. Nora and Mrs. Linde made a healthy conversation they talk about their past life. Nora shares hers secret with Mrs. Linde she tell her that she found satisfaction in her act of taking loan because she had saved her husband's life. Nora's behavior with Mrs. Linde was very pleasant. She asked her husband to help her friend in finding a job toward told Nora that he will surely help her. Mrs. Linde also behave well with Nora. She does not make excuse of Nora that she had forgotten to send a condolence letter on the death of her husband. At first Mrs. Linde suspect that Dr. Rank would be a person who give loan to Nora but Nora told everything to Mrs. Linde that she had taken loan from Kroonstad she asked him to send second letter in which he should not blackmail helmer and Nora Mrs. Linde plays a positive role as a friend. We see Nora's relation with helmer and Mrs. Linde was very pleasant. Self-sacrificing and positive. As a mother she fulfil all roles of a mother. She felt very happy by playing with children. Nora's children was under the care of nurse which was also a caretaker of Nora when she was infant. The relation of Nora with nurse was good. She asks nurse if she would leave her children, what they will feel. At the end, she left her home and does not think about her children. Nora's character has some unpleasant things as well.

For example her tendency to tell lies. She deny that she had eaten macrons or jam. She deny that krogstad had made visit in the absence of Torvalds. She first told Mrs. Linde that she had taken money from her father to make a trip for Italy. She take loan for the treatment of her husband. Whatever was her motive, she had made a lie which shows the degradation of truth. When krogstad makes a threat that he will tell everything to helmer if she did not support him, Nora got frightened. She felt krogstad will create a great trouble for her. Her forge of making signature of her father was a crucial at of her life. She think that she will borrow money from Dr. Rank but Dr. Rank purposes her. He was in love with Nora. It was very dishonor for Nora to ask for money to him. Because at this time talking about money would show that she is making some kind of commitment to Dr. Rank. Many Crisco happen in Nora's life. When helmer told Nora that a liar produces seems on his children and cannot look after then truly, she got mentally disturb the change of behavior of helmer forced Nora of think about herself first and then about her family. She realized that her husband was a selfish man. His principles was genuinely made by him and they are for his happiness. She decided to take a bold step of leaving her home. Nora is represented as a

symbol of liberty of an individual. Her character shows many positive things like her loving and kind nature, her happiness in saving the life of helmer her positive attitude towards Dr. Rank, Ibsen had beautifully portrayed the character of Nora.

As for as the character of Torvald is concerned we can say that it is a true representation of patriarchal society. His patronizing attitude towards Nora shows that for him Nora was a lawyer. He always shows affection for Nora. No doubt he truly loves Nora. But we can see his tone was patronizing. He always regards himself superior. As show that he is a man of Nora principles he stops Nora to spend more money. As mostly tries to explain the value of economy. When Nora asked him to take loan he refused her. He was against taking loan. When Nora ask him to help Mrs. Linde he promised Nora to give a job to her friend in the bank. He tries to show his helpful nature. However, he was strict with his wife as far as his moral principles were concerned. His ego and his self-interest was more important than Nora. He scolds Nora when Nora lies that nobody came in the absence of helmer his relation was good. With Nora in the beginning. But the manner in which he speaks clearly shows he take himself superior. Krogstad was a childhood friend of helmer. His image was not so good in front of helmer. Helmer wanted to dismiss krogstad because of his deception. His view and attitude towards krogstad was not so good if we look on his relation with Dr. Rank it was quite different from the relation of krogstad Dr. Rank was suffering from a serious disease of tuberculosis. He mostly comes to meet with helmer they were used to talk in helmer's study room. Helmer's egoless and selfishness appears when he scolds Nora after reading the first letter of krogstad. He said that he will never love Nora as he loved her before. Their relation will be changed because of Nora's act of taking loan. But when he got second letter he changed his views and pretend that he is obligating Nora for giving again his love. His change of behavior helped Nora to clear her misperception about his love. He shows that he is the master in the house who has laid down rules and his wife has to conform these rules. He teats Nora as his possession. Nora was expecting that he will take the guilt of her action upon himself but he reacted against her thinking. He cones heavily upon her. He was enjoying rights of full ownership over Nora. As we see a change in Nora's character we also find a change in Helmer's character. Nora's change was for liberty but Helmer's change was for self-satisfaction. If we analyses the character of krogstad we can see he was a man who was responsible for creating complications in Nora's life. He was a man from Nora take help. Inspire of taking regular instalment. He blackmailed Nora to persuade helmer to give him higher post in the bank. He take a Nora's forged signature as her weakness and he threatened her. Nora committed that she had forged her father's signature. She told him that she is unable to influence his husband's official decisions. Krogstad's conversation with Nora shows that he was failed to win helmer's favor. He was a childhood friend of helmer. He thought that because of boyhood friendship helmer with not stand against him. But he was wrong in expecting favor from him several years ago, krogstad and Christine had been lovers but because of some problems Christine had to marry with another man. This thing made krogstad disappointed. When Mrs. Linde offers him to marry he felt very happy. At the proposal of marriage he felt his suit that he had thereat Nora because of nothing. He release that Nora was not at fault Mrs. Linde's marriage proposal brings a change of heart in krogstad. He wrote a letter of regret to Nora and expressed his repellece to Nora over his first letter. We can see krogstad was not an evil-minded person. It was true that at one time he tempted to commit a criminal act by threatening Nora but with the passage of time he realized his mistake made a repentance letter and let Nora free from debt. As for as the character of Mrs. Linde is concerned we can say that she was a very noble lady having many positive traits. When she was young, she had a love affair but because love of her ill mother and two young brother she had to marry with a rich man. Mrs. Linde was an old friend of Nora she came to see Nora after the death of her husband. After the death of her husband her mother was also died. Her brother left her and got busy in their lives. Mrs. Linde's life was purposeless as she had no one to live for. She was in search of a job. She asked Nora to help for finding a job. She tells Nora that a she felt no repentance because she was forced by the circumstances. She says she was very happy and satisfied because she was able to make her ailing mother's life a little easier and

4.2. Symbolism in Doll's House

Symbolism is a literary term originated Italy in 19th century. It is a literary device employed by the writer to convey implied meaning in a way, it is here sign or symbols stand for something not oblivious. As far as "A Doll's House" by "Henrik Ibsen" is covered it is fully of suggestiveness. Ibsen has concerned artistic use of symbolism in this play to convey implicate and explicit meanings. The very little of the Doll's House is suggestive a woman's house has been called "A Doll's House" which employs that a women is no more than a doll that is inanimate, a commodity and totally at the mercy of her male members, she is just like a doll to be played with so, symbolism starts from the title of the play. The title relates rightly with there and story.

Nora's house can be considered "A Doll's House". In the light of her relationship with her husband, batter and children. All for separate reasons. There is use of symbols in the lay at different places. Ibsen has some "philosophy for symbolism". In this play that is a person will never remain happy when put down in the mound of something else.

There is symbolism at the level of naming. The persons of naming show the relationship between the name and named. The way Nora is named indicated that she does not have an equal status. She is not given human status. Rather she is named after animals names. There is also symbolism in the use of lexis. The use of word little be little's her status. One thing is noteworthy that the wild bird cannot be changed. But ironically Hermer forget that

these wild birds from their very nature love to be free and not in cage. On one hand, Helmer associates Nora with wideness and on the other wants her to be bully under his control. So, it show that Helmer was totally in dark about his wisher regarding his wife. Actually these symbols make the ground for the end where Nora prefers to fly rather than being caged. The use of symbols was oblivious from the lines given below.

“My little song bird must not drop his wings” and much more. The things wrapped in mystery symbolize mysterious relationship between Nora and her husband.

Time and time again Nora chapping her hands like a child. She get exited very soon. For example Nora (clapping your hands) what are you doing? The repetition of word symbolize that she is uncertain. In patriarchal society. A woman usually is deprived of self-confidence she wants her ideas and deeds certified by a man. Nora repeats the words which illustrates lack of confidence on her part. Most of the lines uttered by Nora symbolize her mental confusion and rootlessness. As the play progress, we can sense that coming dangers Nora is uncertain like most of the women whether she will be able to hang with her husband in future on non. For example “something is coming now” No, actually it is one of the hurdle and no one will come attest today.

The line mentioned above symbolize her sense of being them in many selves. The use of word ‘empty’ symbolizes ‘emptiness’ or ‘shallowness’ of Nora’s life.

Moreover, the use of word ‘employ’ symbolize that life is like a better box it is walled and apparently protected but from inside it is empty and full of deceptions. The dress nurse brings for Nora is in want of mending. But in the course of paly, that it was never in a position to e mended. The torn dress symbolize gap between Nora and her husband. For the time being, things are going well but cannot last for long. The lines are quoted above are very symbolic.

The words uttered by Nora “taking off my fancy dress”. Symbolize that she wants to get rid of troubles or she is coming toward the reality and right and putting off the mask she has been wearing so far, and acting like a puppet. Dance symbolizes compromises in Nora’s life and her survival depends on her dancing and dancing she has been surviving so far there is Helmer’s House by attracting him with her physical charms. A woman usually is valued for her beauty not for ideas. So she is treated as a “Sex doll” as Nora in the play. The lines uttered by Helmer are very symbolical in nature where shall, I protected like a hunted dove.

The word hunting dove is symbolical because Krogstad is continuously in Nora’s search. She is in danger and hence hunted. The word not “Konwing” symbolize lack of knowledge of a woman Nora is perceived as less wise and knowledge able. As Helmer says “I will advise you and directs you”. In Christianity, Christmas is an important family celebrating event. At Christmas families forgets their interior problems and come close to family by spearing time and having lunch and dinner with family. But here at Nora’s house everything was opposite.

And by the passage of time finally times come when all very leaf of appearance fall down and one is left bare or single to full the reality. That was a New Year day. And New Year’s Day is a traditionally viewed as the beginning of play looking forward to just a new start. Torvalds is because of a start of a new and well paid job at bank and Nora anticipates bring free form the debt. But ironically she was forced by the circumstance to be free from her husband and children. Mrs. Linde and Krogsted begin a new life agter long period of suffering and Dr. Rank dies. And it seems as the end of play or transition according to one’s point of view. So every character in the paly start a new life respectively whether favorable or not. So, the word symbolizes a sudden change that takes place suddenly. So, the dance of Nora symbolizes that she was tired of wearing appearances and wants to get rid of this poison. So, her final decision to leave her husband and children symbolize that one cannot live a life of deceptions fore over. Finally, one has to decide between the two and Nora’s bold step of leaving her husband and children symbolizes an element of change on part of woman to locate their “independent identity”. Now, Most of the women have realized that things don’t happen themselves but brought to happen. The bold step taken by Nora is a message for the other to take imitative for change. Nora is torch-bearer of change of a feminist.

4.3. Conflict between woman and existing society.

We can regard this drama as a drama of ideas. It goes for beyond most of the tragedies of Ibsen’s time on the continents. The women in this play revel a revolt against the rules of society. Women were strong enough to made right choices. However, it is only in the great dreams of ideas that characters are able to express themselves fully. To analyses the conflict between women and the existing society of Victorian era, we try to explore up to what extent women exploit, the social norms. First the bold step of Nora show that, she was no more bound by the society. She tried to make herself independent and wants her own identity which was not acceptable at that time. The time in which drama was written, the society was in sport of male dominance. Nora’s act of leaving home, anchor the foundation of feminisms. The major issues of existing society in which drama was written are given below.

- i. Contradictions.
- ii. Poverty.
- iii. Industrial exploitation.
- iv. Religious unrest
- v. Women suffrage

Now we see up to what extend these issues are explodes in the life of women of Ibsen’s drama as far as the life of Nora is concerned, she faced many contradictions throughout her life. Inspire of Helmer’s advice she take loan to

save the life of Helmer. She also forged the signature of her father. For Nora, the health of Helmer was more important than her crime of taking money secretly.

Poverty was another prominent issue of that time. We can see because of poverty, Nora was forced to take money from Krogstad and forged father. Poverty was very prominent issue of that age. Because of poverty Christine leave her lover and married with a rich man. If we anguses the life of Nurse, we come to know because of poverty she left her body on the road. It was a very disastrous thing for a mother to leave her body alone.

Another prominent element of Victorian area is women suffrage. The life of Christin and the life of Nurse are best example of women suffrage. Ibsen has portrayed very beautifully the women characters. His characters implicitly explore the condition of society. Of that time. When Nora leaves her home, she did not think of her children and did not care the sayings of religion her care lessens, about religion shows the religious unrest of present time. Nora made herself more important than her family, Norms of society. And forget about the problems of future life which a woman faced in the absence of the support of Male. For example, we can take the life of Christine life faced many problems to maintain herself after the death of her husband.

4.4. Illusion and reality in doll's house

The element of illusion is present in all characters. However Nora creates much illusion than others. In the beginning of the play, Nora breaks the trust of Helmer by taking money from Krogstad and forging the signature of her father. Although her mother was positive. At the end Helmer does not give importance to her motive when he came to know about the mistakes of Nora, this is the best example of reality that our motives are devalued in front of our mistakes Nora lead a life of phantasy. She was confident that Helmer love her a lot and will take all the responsibility on his shoulders. But the reality was opposite of her thinking the reality becomes clear in front of Nora when Helmer loses his temper. And rudely behave with Nora. When Nora came out of the illusion of Helmer's love she found herself strong enough to leave her family. For her Helmer was a moralist who value his principles more than anything but leads Nora to her fact that he was a selfish man illusion on the part of Helmer is that he love Nora. But he gives more important to himself. And reputation after reading the first letter "He was much worried about the public disclosure than of Nora. For him his reputation comes first than his relationship with Nora. The life of Christine shows illusion and reality both. Christine was a young girl which along to the poor family she was in love with Krogstad. But she ditches Krogstad and married to Mr. Linde. After the marriage some time his husband suddenly died. At the time of her marriage she can inform Krogstad about her marriage but she did not do that. She was just doing this marriage to make family problems easy. Now reality lies in this sense that her motive was devalue in front of her out of marriage. On the part, of Nora, Christen also create illusion to Nora when she meet Krogstad, she forced him not to black mail Nora. But she asked krogstad to inform Helmer about the crimes of Nora. Christen had got maturity from the difficulties of life which she faced after the death of Mr. Linde. She wants to make Nora mature that's why she forced krogstad to inform Helmer and not to made public disloure. This act of Christine is the most important act of the play because upon this Nora was able to come out of the form Christine. Because he loves Christine and want to marry her. However, Christine married to Mr. Linde. But Krogstad still loves her and want to take her.

After some time when Helmer takes his job he makes a non – moral act by threatening Nora to force Helmer to give him a high post in the bank. In spite of getting regular installment from Nora he made Nora in a state of mental disturbance.

If we see the life of Krogstad, we come to know that he was a depressed man who first of all dis hearted by losing his love, then by the death of his wife. He made wrong statements in the bank which results his job in danger. The tension of losing job forced him to blackmail Nora. But at the end when Christine came to his life, the psychological condition of his mind changed. He wrote second letter of repentance of Helmer. He assured Helmer that he will not made any kind of public disclosure. We can also analyze illusion in the character of Dr. Rank. He shows that he is ill and his condition is serious. He comes to meet Helmer because he want to forget about his disease. Inwardly he was in love with Nora and Nora did not response to his intention. She was faithful to her husband. On one moment of Nora's life when she was blackmailed by Krogstad, she thought of taking money from Dr. Rank and return all of Krogstad's money back. But before asking money Dr. Rank proposed her. She did not response to his proposal and keep silent because at this movement if she demands money means that she has to follow the intention of Dr. Rank. The silence of Nora shows her strength.

4.5. Nora As A Symbol of Self-Independence

At that time, when Nora leaves hume the self- intendance of woman does not exist. If we see the past life of Nora, she was like a doll of her father who simply transferred to her husband's hand.

Nora proves to be a devoted wife and loving mother. At the beginning of te play she was not independent. She do needle work to earn money. Whatever she earns does not spend on her self because she was bound to pay regular installments. She loved eating macrons. But she eat them secretly. This shows that at the beginning she was not independent even to eat of her own choice.

She wears dress of Helmer's choice at a fancy dress party. For her it was necessary to act upon the advice of Helmer. Because she respected his ego. This shows that Nora made many self- sacrifices because she was bound to lead the good domestic life. But at the end of drama we see a remarkable change in her thinking behavior and actions. She supports her own view that one should sincere first to his self and then to others.

Which is the most sacred thing. Her steps shows she was a great symbol of self- independence for the women of Victorian era.

When Knogstand demands guarantee for loan she forged signature which should that she was not independent to sign openly.

4.6. A Socialist Play

This play has been regarded as a socialist play because it raise the basic social problem of man and woman that is “equality”. Nora do many efforts for Helmer when se was bound but at the end she made herself independent. The relation of Nora and Helmer was of eight to nine years, we can see throughout their relation duration Nora does not found equality with Helmer. The break up of their relation shows men also have their identity. Although we found the objectives of first and second wave of feminism in this drama but we does not found equality in any relation either it was the relation of Nora and Helmer and the relation of Christine and Krogstad. We compare this drama with a social drama as it deals with many social issues as well we can see in this drama. The life of Nurse and life of Christine are the examples of women suffrage class difference in Nurse and Mrs. Linde that why Nurse always remain poor and Mrs. Linde was free and able to marry again. If Mrs. Linde does not marry at that time may be she always remained a lower class girl. It is a socialist play because characters of this play deal with all those social problems which a common man and woman faced at that time. This work of Ibsen is very remarkable from the point of view of socialism. The end of drama brings a appreciative social change. The end of drama created an endless debate at that time. Modern researches have shown society changes with time. The change in the character of Nora is not so surprising. Her step showed the difference of male and female power should be equal. If a man can be independent in making his decisions and woman can also be independent in her decisions.

5. Conclusion

My research ends with how gender roles are constructed in the first revolutionary modern drama. Ibsen has beautifully explored the condition of marginalized women of that time. When the drama was written the existing society had no concept of feminism. Women were restricted to the household as they were expected inferior creature but man were supposed to be the symbol of world power, symbol of authority, symbol of reputation and symbol of superiority. He was the head regarded as the decision maker. By going through the drama, we analyze that this position of man at that time is clearly elaborated by Ibsen. When Nora says, I simply transferred from my father’s hand to my husband’s hand, her words show the decision power of man. Throughout the drama, Nora made many sacrifices and had faced many challenges by remaining consistent. The work of Ibsen is a best example for the foundation of feminism. The work of Shakespeare in Hamlet and Oscar Wild’s work I the picture of dorian gray shows male dominance. But in their work, we find not so many support for women. As in the work of Ibsen we can see had changed the thinking of women of that time. He gave a message, through his literary work that women should fight for their rights, they also posses identity. They should be independent in their thoughts and in their deeds. When Nora was leaving she said, it is a very sacred thing that one should be sincere first to him/her self than to others. Her words can be regarded as a message of independence. We find a hope at the end of drama that with the passage of time when women start thinking of themselves they will come to known what are the basic rights about which they can fight then they will stop realizing themselves as a inferior figure of the society. Some is the case with Nora. At the end she realizes her importance and left Helmer to make herself free Ibsen has artistically designed gender roles by using his literary efforts. His work is a real picture of true condition of society of Victorian age.

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